

THE INFLUENCE OF MATRIX DEFORMATION ON TENSILE BEHAVIOR IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The influence of matrix plasticity on the deformation and properties of continuously-reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) has not been well-established. Much of the information on local stresses and strains in continuously-reinforced Ti- and Ti-aluminide MMC's is inferred from theoretical, rather than experimental, studies. In this paper, quantitative effects of matrix yield strain and work-hardening characteristics on global and local response of MMC's are briefly discussed from such theoretical perspectives. However, while theoretical studies can provide a reasonable assessment of the role of bulk matrix characteristics on local and global MMC response, the current formulations are based on the assumptions of homogeneous and isotropic matrix behavior, which are often not valid in advanced MMCs. In addition, modeling approaches typically do not adequately account for matrix damage. Such inhomogeneous and damage-related responses of the matrix can significantly alter local stresses and strains, which control failure conditions. Experimental studies to investigate matrix deformation and damage in Ti-based metal matrix composites will be described.

Keywords: metal matrix composites, continuous reinforcements, Ti-aluminide, SiC fibers, deformation, matrix plasticity, damage

1. INTRODUCTION

Theoretical and experimental studies of the influence of composite constituents on composite properties have typically emphasized either the properties of reinforcements or of interfaces in MMC's. However, little attention has been given to understanding and establishing the role of matrix properties on composite deformation and properties. A fundamental knowledge of how basic matrix properties and characteristics influence composite properties is required to guide matrix development for improved composite performance, and to provide for realistic strength and life prediction. Matrix constitutive properties depend sensitively on matrix microstructure and composition (including impurity content); and the yield strength, work hardening behavior, strain-to-failure, elastic modulus, and fracture toughness may all vary significantly with changes in matrix microstructure and chemical composition. A good understanding of these individual effects is required to guide compositional control and microstructural development through pre- and post-consolidation thermo-mechanical treatments of MMC's.

While significant activity has been directed toward understanding the effect of matrix deformation and damage on the properties of discontinuously-reinforced composites, their influence on continuously-reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) has not been well-established. Much of the information concerning the local stresses and strains that develop from thermal and mechanical loads in continuously-reinforced Ti- and Ti-aluminide MMC's is inferred from theoretical, rather than experimental, studies. Such calculations can provide a reasonable assessment of the role of bulk matrix characteristics on local and global MMC response, and can therefore be useful as a tool for general guidance on improved MMC architecture and processing conditions. While the elastic response of the matrix and reinforcements are well-described by the various models employed, current theoretical formulations are based on the assumptions of

homogeneous and isotropic plastic behavior of the matrix, which are generally not observed in advanced composite matrix alloys. Additionally, aspects of damage, which are much more dominant in MMCs compared with monolithic metals, have received little attention. Such inhomogeneous and damage-related responses of the matrix, some which are briefly discussed in this paper, can significantly alter local stresses and strains compared with homogeneous conditions, resulting in non-conservative assessments of MMC strength and fatigue life. It is not clear how inhomogeneous matrix behavior may be addressed with the required degree of complexity from a theoretical perspective. In many cases, it therefore appears expedient to experimentally investigate the local deformation mechanisms and response in advanced MMC's, so that guidance on improved modeling requirements may be provided.

The intent of this paper is to consider and discuss several aspects of matrix plasticity, and to explore their potential significance with respect to the deformation and properties of continuously-reinforced MMC's. A brief discussion of theoretical approaches to address matrix plasticity is provided in the following section, and is followed by a discussion of the potential effects of several components of matrix plasticity, including elastic yield strain, work-hardening rate, and deformation mode (homogeneous vs. inhomogeneous), on the global and local response of MMC's. This paper will focus on continuously-reinforced Ti- and Ti-aluminide composites, although results of studies in other systems (such as Cu/W, and discontinuously-reinforced Al/SiC) will be incorporated where relevant. Experimental techniques required to establish the magnitude and significance of matrix deformation will be discussed, and experimental studies will be suggested.

2. COMPOSITE MODELING

A significant number of modeling studies have provided insight into the deformation of MMCs [1-16]. Much of the progress and success has been in modeling the longitudinal orientation of unidirectional MMCs, where loads approach axisymmetric conditions, making analyses simpler, and where the global response is dominated by the elastic response of the high modulus fiber. Significant advances have been made in the modeling of matrix plasticity under a wide range of loading conditions (monotonic vs. time-dependent), stress states, and temperatures [1-16]. Progress has also been made in the ability to account for various forms of damage, such as interface debonding [7,10,11,17] and fiber cracking [18], although in the case of the former the analyses so far are limited to finite element method (FEM) solutions.

However, while good agreement with limited experimental data is often cited as validation of various models, the need for more rigorous experimental verification based on microstructural analyses and comprehensive mechanical measurements has been emphasized [19,20]. This point is emphasized Figures 1a and 1b taken from [19,21], where the stress-strain and Poisson's ratio responses for a 90° SCS-6/Ti-15V-3Cr-3Sn-3Al (Ti-15-3) MMC are compared with the AGLPLY model based on the vanishing fiber diameter model of [1], and the unit cell model of [10]. Debonding and the additional plasticity associated with this process is not accounted for in the AGLPLY model. On the other hand, a zero bond strength, with debonding and additional plasticity, were accounted for in the unit cell model (FEM solution). Thus, whereas both models provided good correlation with experimental data in Figure 1a, the Poisson's ratio data in Figure 1b clearly shows that the AGLPLY model was unable to provide adequate correlation, in spite of the modification. Additionally, it is extremely important to recognize that *local* stresses and strains must be determined accurately, since they control damage evolution and failure. The utility of a model for structural design purposes, and for providing an adequate understanding of the physical processes involved in the deformation, damage accumulation, and failure of advanced MMC's, is significantly diminished when experimental evidence shows that a model does not adequately predict global or local response.

Current continuum models for MMCs treat the matrix as a homogeneous medium with constitutive properties that are independent of location in the composite. However, a number of extrinsic effects may lead to non-uniformity in matrix properties and response, including (a) inhomogeneities in the matrix composition and microstructure near the fiber/matrix interface due to chemical reactions with the reinforcement (Figure 2), (b) anisotropic deformation of the matrix caused by texture effects, (c) local damage in the reinforcement, at the interface, or in the matrix and (d) non-uniformities in the composite architecture, such as those resulting from non-uniform fiber spacings and the presence of fiber cross-weaves (e.g. Mo-weaves). Except for damage, which is just beginning to be addressed [23,24], these issues of non-homogeneities have not been addressed in the continuum literature.

In addition to extrinsic effects, many advanced matrices, including those based on Ti- and Ti-aluminide alloys, deform in an intrinsically inhomogeneous fashion [19,25,26]. Continuum approaches have a fundamental difficulty in adequately addressing such intrinsic inhomogeneous deformation of the matrix, primarily because the micro-constitutive responses are not adequately defined, and a simple method of evaluating them (including the characteristics of interfaces at the appropriate microstructural level, such as alpha-2/beta interfaces [26]) does not exist. Rather, an initial approach may be to experimentally determine the local deformation and damage response, and utilize an iterative procedure to arrive at estimates of the constitutive response at the microscopic level of the matrix.

The occurrence of inhomogeneous deformation has been established experimentally in a number of composite systems [17,19,21,23,24,27,28]. However, the magnitude and extent of inhomogeneous deformation have not been determined in any detail, and this is particularly true for continuously-reinforced MMC's. As a result, the impact of inhomogeneous matrix deformation, and the importance of matrix deformation in general, on the properties of continuously-reinforced MMC's has not been clearly established. Careful experimental work is required to establish the importance and role of matrix plasticity. The potential importance of several aspects of matrix plasticity is discussed in the following sections.

3. MATRIX PLASTICITY

From the point of view of MMC fabrication, the overriding emphasis in matrix deformation has been on matrix ductility, typically quantified in terms of the reduction-of-area, or in terms of the strain-to-failure at the temperature of interest. From the viewpoint of MMC deformation, the strain-to-failure of conventional Al- and Ti-based matrices is probably not significant for 0° laminates, since the failure strain of these alloys is significantly larger than that of SiC monofilaments (typically about 1%). However, the limited strain-to-failure of the less ductile intermetallic-based matrices (such as Ti- and Ni-aluminides) is likely to be an important factor, since the failure strains (often $\leq 1.5\%$) are comparable to the fiber failure strain and the effective plastic strains (including residual stress effects) experienced by the matrix in the MMC. In addition, the magnitude of the strain-to-failure is extremely important for off-axis loading (such as 90° lamina), where intense plasticity and damage around debonded fibers can drastically reduce the strength and global failure strain of the MMC. Aside from this issue of failure strain, other plasticity parameters of the matrix have significant influence on the overall MMC response. These parameters include the yield (or elastic) strain, work-hardening rate, fracture toughness, fatigue response, and creep and environmental resistance of the matrix. Addressing all these issues is outside the scope of this paper, and in the next three sections we shall discuss effects of yield strain, work hardening rate, and inhomogeneous deformation of the matrix. The experimental approach, and the results of initial experiments to measure local deformation and investigate damage mechanisms will also be described.

In the following sections, discussion will focus on 0° MMC's, where the global response is dominated by the elastic behavior of the fibers. For 90° MMC's, the requirements on matrix yield strength, strain to failure, and work-hardening are even more important. This is because debonding of the fiber causes severe strain/stress concentrations around the fiber, leading to matrix failure, either in a ductile mode (microvoid coalescence) or in a quasi-brittle fashion. That is why strength of 90° MMC's are typically well below those of the matrix. Clearly, improvement of the properties of the 90° MMC's requires a strong, tough, and ductile matrix.

3.1 Yield Strain

A bilinear yield response is observed in 0° Cu/W composites [5,29,30], and the transition point occurs at the yield strain (ϵ_y) of the (Cu) matrix. This strain is very low ($\sim 0.03\%$) because of the low yield strength ($\sigma_y \sim 30\text{MPa}$), and so the stress/strain curve and failure of the MMC is dominated by the work-hardening behavior (hardening rate, H) of the matrix and the modulus and volume fraction (V_f) of the fiber [29,30]. Such behavior has also been observed for the Al/alumina system [31]. In Ti- and Ti-aluminide composites, the yield strain of the matrix is much closer to the failure strain of the reinforcing fiber most often employed (SiC, SCS-6), and so the yield strength/strain are anticipated to have a dominant effect on elastic-plastic behavior and failure strength of the MMC.

The effects of σ_y (or ϵ_y) on the elastic-plastic response of a Ti-based MMC are considered analytically below, using unidirectional 35 volume percent SiC (SCS-6) fiber-reinforced Ti-15-3 matrix as the model system, loaded in the fiber direction. The matrix has a yield strength of approximately 710 MPa and an elastic modulus (E) of approximately 91 GPa at room temperature (RT), resulting in a yield strain of 0.8%. Other values of matrix and fiber properties may be obtained from [11,19,25]. An elastic-plastic concentric cylinder model [12] is used to calculate the MMC response, assuming a linear work hardening response ($d\sigma/d\epsilon=H=3.2$ GPa at RT) for the matrix. The Prandtl-Reuss flow rule used for the plastic analysis is

$$d\epsilon_{ij}^P = d\lambda S_{ij}; \quad d\lambda = (3/2)[(1-m)/H]d\sigma_e/\sigma_e \quad (1)$$

where $m=H/E$, $d\epsilon_{ij}^P$ are the incremental plastic strain components, S_{ij} are the deviatoric stresses, and $\sigma_e = \{(3/2)S_{ij}S_{ij}\}^{1/2}$. The time-independent elastic-plastic calculations assumed cooling to RT from the processing temperature of 815 C, followed by loading to various stress levels, so that thermal residual stresses were accounted for in the calculations. The yield strength was then parametrically varied, while holding the thermal properties constant, in order to estimate the effects of flow stress on the elastic-plastic response of the MMC. In addition, the effective plastic strain (ϵ^P) in the matrix immediately adjacent to the fiber was calculated using the relationship: $\epsilon^P = \{(1-m)/H\}(\sigma_e - \sigma_y)$, where σ_e was obtained from the elastic-plastic calculations. ϵ^P provided a measure of local matrix deformation.

Figure 3a shows the effects of yield strength on (i) the global stress-strain response of the MMC and (ii) the local plastic strain in the matrix adjacent to the fiber for a composite with $V_f=0.35$ and a strain-hardening slope of 3.2 GPa. The data indicated by circles correspond to the baseline response, and the triangles and squares represent yield strengths of 80% and 50% of the base yield strength, respectively. As anticipated, Figure 3a illustrates that the yield strength has a strong influence on the elastic-plastic response of the MMC. Note that for a σ_y of 355 MPa, the matrix yielded on cooling (prior to mechanical loading), although the zone of yielding had not extended to the entire matrix. Also, the local plastic strains were reasonably small with respect to failure strains typical of Ti-based MMCs.

The calculations also indicate that the fiber stress at a given applied mechanical strain is insensitive to the values of σ_y and H. The line BB in Figure 3a corresponds to the MMC strain at which the fiber stress reaches a value of 3200 MPa (say, the critical fiber strength), and it is independent of the yield strength of the matrix. Thus, if failure is governed simply by the fiber strength, then the analysis indicates that the failure strain of the MMC should be independent of the matrix yield strength (or yield strain), provided the thermal expansion characteristics remain the same. The only available data on the effects of yield strength on the elastic-plastic response of Ti-alloy based MMC are available in [32], where the yield strength of the matrix was varied from 820 MPa to 1460 MPa for the SCS6/Ti-15-3 system by using different heat treatments on specimens obtained from the same panel. The heat treatments also considerably altered the failure strain of the matrix; from approximately 22% for the weakest matrix to only 1.3% for the strongest matrix. The longitudinal (0°) MMC data indicated that the composite failure strain changed with matrix conditions, rather than remaining constant; and the MMC with the intermediate matrix failure strain had the highest strain to failure. At the same time, however, the concentric cylinder model was able to predict the shape of the observed *global* stress-strain curve extremely well. One explanation for the inability to predict the failure strength/strain is that there may be *local* damage processes (such as reaction-zone cracks and inhomogeneous matrix deformation) active, which may have had significant influence on failure, but whose effect on the global stress-strain response was small. It is not clear whether the yield strength or the failure strain of the matrix was responsible for the observed failure strain behavior of the MMC's, since both yield strength and failure strain were changed simultaneously. A detailed, systematic microstructural study would be useful to provide a better understanding of the deformation and damage processes responsible for the behavior of this system.

3.2 Work-hardening

The important effect of matrix work-hardening on the properties of discontinuously-reinforced Al MMC's [33] and W fiber-reinforced Cu-based MMC's is well-documented [5,29,30]. However, the effect of work-hardening on the behavior of continuously-reinforced Ti-based MMC's is not well-studied. Figure 3b shows the calculated effect of altering the work-hardening rate from a value of 3.2 GPa to 12.8 GPa on the axial properties of a 0° Ti-15-3/SiC composite,

while maintaining the same matrix yield strength. The figure illustrates that the work-hardening rate is anticipated to have negligible influence on the global axial elastic-plastic response of the MMC. This effect is well below that for the Cu/W system, where H dominated the elastic-plastic response of the MMC [29]. Note that for the Cu/W system, the ratio σ_y/H was approximately 0.0042 compared with 0.18 for the Ti-based system considered here. Thus, σ_y and H both influence the axial response of the MMC. Figure 3b also indicates that the effect of H in reducing the local plastic matrix strain at the fiber/matrix interface, although small, can be significant at small inelastic MMC strains near the macroscopic "yield" strain of the MMC. This characteristic may be important where design allowance must be made for limited yielding of the matrix.

Work-hardening is also likely to be important for redistributing loads in the vicinity of fiber fractures. The load from a cracked fiber has to be taken up either by the matrix, or by adjacent fibers. If the matrix material work-hardens significantly, then the matrix can locally support some of the load originally carried by the fiber, thereby reducing the redistribution of load to adjacent fibers (ie, "shielding"). However, if the matrix does not work-harden, then the stress singularity associated with fiber fracture can lead to intense localized plastic deformation of the matrix (observed microscopically [19]), and such plasticity under constrained total axial strain may in turn cause local unloading of the matrix. Under such conditions, adjacent fibers must not only support the load originally carried by the cracked fiber, but also some of the load originally in the matrix surrounding the cracked fiber. This combination may lead to failure of the adjacent fibers. Matrix work-hardening would be beneficial in shielding adjacent fibers from the stress concentration associated with cracked fibers. For example, delocalized periodic fiber fragmentation is observed after deformation at RT in continuously-reinforced Ti-24Al-11Nb/SiC composites, where the work-hardening rate of the matrix is 2.5 GPa. However, fiber damage becomes very localized at 815 C, where the work-hardening rate of the matrix approaches zero [34].

A related issue when discussing matrix plasticity in MMC's is the effect of fiber volume fraction, which has a large influence on the residual stresses. Figure 3b shows the calculated effect of increased fiber volume fraction on the 0° MMC response and the local plastic strain. The figure shows the expected beneficial effect of increased fiber volume fraction on the load carrying ability of the MMC for a given applied strain. The residual fiber stress from cooling decreases from approximately -430 MPa to -140 MPa for V_f of 0.35 and 0.70, respectively, and these are small compared with fiber strengths. Figure 3b also indicates that an increased V_f will not lead to an increase in local plastic strain, for the same imposed axial strain. Therefore, if matrix damage through plastic straining were an important factor in causing failure, then the analysis suggests that the volume fraction of fibers would not be a major variable. However, it is important to recognize that a higher V_f is often associated with touching fibers, which would be major crack initiation sites. Additionally, detrimental effects on in-situ matrix properties, such as hardening [22] and embrittlement, caused by diffusion of species (such as C) from the fiber into the matrix is enhanced for higher V_f MMC's. These issues of in-situ matrix behavior have not been studied in detail, but need special attention for arriving at rational design approaches for desirable MMC architectures.

3.3 Deformation Mode (Homogeneous, Inhomogeneous, and Damage)

The mode of matrix deformation is often assumed to be homogeneous and uniform, with the matrix elastic-plastic behavior determined by testing matrix panels. This is likely to be a reasonable approach in a number of technologically significant MMC systems, including Cu-MMC's and some Al-MMC's. However, the possible effects of inhomogeneous matrix deformation (slip localization, grain boundary sliding, anisotropic plastic properties, etc.), and damage are only beginning to be addressed. The latter would include matrix cracking, and microvoid nucleation and growth, caused by enhanced stresses and plasticity at fiber-matrix debonds, reaction-zone cracks, and at fiber cracks and fiber ends. Also, it may be important to distinguish between uniform (homogeneous) strain and total strain, which includes a component of non-uniform strain. Detailed experimental studies are required to document and understand the occurrence and effects of inhomogeneous deformation and damage.

A number of studies have documented the occurrence of non-homogeneous deformation and damage in metallic composites [for example, 17-21,23,27-29 and references therein]. Figures 4a and 4b illustrate slip bands observed in both 0° and 90° SCS6/Ti-15-3 MMCs under tensile loading at RT. The planarity of slip and shear localization was caused by precipitation of an extremely fine omega phase in the beta Ti-alloy matrix [19]. The evolution [21] and morphology

of plastic deformation in the 0° MMC do not agree with continuum models, which predict that plasticity should spread in the form of cylinders surrounding a fiber. Rather, slip is extremely inhomogeneous, being associated with reaction-zone cracks during the "pre-yield" regime of deformation; also, the density of slip bands varied from one grain to another. The deformation of the 90° MMC was even more inhomogeneous, with intense slip bands forming between adjacent fibers, as observed in Figure 4b, and was not well-predicted by the elastic-plastic models. A damage model was used to explain slip localization and strain-to-failure of the 90° MMC [24], and this did provide better agreement with experiments. However, the analyses need to be validated by local measurements of strain since, as already mentioned, global MMC behavior is dominated by the fiber, which tends to mask out local deformation patterns of the matrix. A damage approach was also attempted to explain the low strain-to-fracture in Al-based whisker-reinforced MMCs [23].

Microstructural inhomogeneities can also lead to inhomogeneous deformation. This type of behavior has been observed in Ti-24Al-11Nb based MMCs, where a beta-depleted zone around the fiber can lead to premature cracking of the matrix. It is still not clear what type of non-homogeneous deformation exists around the fiber, and what the local constitutive behavior of the matrix is. This lack of information has prevented accurate assessments of the role of the beta-depleted zone on MMC response. In fact, recent experiments using TEM and channeling patterns [22] suggest that dislocation densities are actually higher around the fiber, contrary to the common expectation that a beta-depleted zone should have lower plasticity. Clearly, the local deformation mechanisms and strains need to be assessed before arriving at a conclusion regarding the role of inhomogeneous matrix microstructure. Other aspects of microstructural inhomogeneities include the diffusion of carbon into the matrix from SiC fibers. Recent hardness profile measurements in Ti-24Al-11Nb/SiC (SCS-6) composites have shown a hardened zone surrounding the fibers, which corresponded to the region of enhanced C concentration [22]; in fact, C stabilizes the alpha-2 phase, thereby producing the beta-depleted zone. Also, thermo-mechanical fatigue experiments on SCS-6/Ti-15-3 have indicated that C-rich zones at ply interfaces are primary sites for cracking, indicating that they likely have lower strain-to-failure than the rest of the matrix. Again, there is no data in the literature to indicate what the local matrix properties are in the carbon-rich zones around a fiber.

4. TECHNIQUES TO MEASURE MATRIX PLASTICITY

There are two specific reasons for the experimental measurement of composite deformation and matrix plasticity. First, experimental determination of the magnitude and extent of matrix plasticity will allow existing models to be validated, and will provide a firm basis for improvement in the accuracy and predictive capabilities of composite modeling approaches. Second, experimental studies can provide critical data required for the timely development of composites. The development of MMC's is currently proceeding by the iterative modification of matrix microstructure and composition, interface properties, and reinforcements. Modeling requires an extensive data base of physical and mechanical properties, including dependencies on temperature, strain rate, and stress state. In addition, both static and time-dependent properties are required. Finally, the ability to account for potential modes of damage is required. This extensive information is available only for a few matrix alloys, and would be prohibitively difficult to obtain for each composite system of interest in an iterative composite development program. Experimental techniques offer the possibility of measuring matrix response directly, and so may be a valuable "real-time" tool in the development of improved MMC's. However, this requires that an understanding of the effect of matrix response on composite properties is available. Careful, systematic studies to establish the correlation between matrix properties, such as matrix plasticity, on the behavior of MMC's is therefore required.

Many experimental techniques have been employed over the years to document matrix plasticity in inhomogeneous solids. These techniques include dislocation etch pitting [35,36], slip band etching [19,28], optical interferometry of surface slip steps [37], Moire interferometry [38], electron channeling [39,40], photoelastic techniques (including surface birefringent coating) [41 and references therein], transmission electron microscopy (TEM) [42], and various strain mapping techniques utilizing fiducial reference marks or naturally-occurring contrast along with stereo-imaging or digital cross-correlation to determine in-plane displacement fields [43,44]. X-ray and neutron diffraction techniques have been employed to determine the elastic matrix strain [for example, 45]. The overall utility of these techniques depends upon the ease of use, consideration

of the sources and magnitude of measurement errors, the spatial resolution, the ability to determine operative deformation mechanisms, and the ability to quantify the local strain fields.

Those techniques that have the ability to quantify the magnitude of matrix plastic strain with a high degree of spatial resolution are likely to be the most useful with respect to collaboration with the modeling community, and to establish an understanding of the effects of matrix plasticity on composite performance. Most of the techniques mentioned above possess a reasonably high spatial resolution. However, digital strain mapping, stereo imaging, and Moire interferometry possess the best ability to quantify the local displacement fields. Channeling patterns can be made semi-quantitative with the aid of appropriate deformation standards (matrix samples loaded to specific strain levels) [22,40], although grain-to-grain inhomogeneities in deformation make a quantitative determination difficult. While each of these techniques have specific limitations in overall utility, techniques such as these (or techniques not yet developed) are nevertheless necessary to provide an experimental basis for understanding the role of matrix plasticity.

Work is now in progress utilizing digital imaging to measure and understand various aspects of composite performance [46,47]. In this technique, images of a region of interest are obtained before and after deformation, and the two images are digitized and compared through one of many available correlation algorithms. The in-plane displacement fields may be determined directly by this process, from which in-plane shear, normal, and principal strains may be determined. Out-of-plane displacements are also measurable with this technique [48]. Fiducial reference grids (Figure 5) can enhance the process of image correlation, and are currently being used for various studies of matrix deformation in continuously-reinforced MMC's [47].

Several techniques allow indirect study of the influence of matrix plasticity. Non-destructive evaluation (NDE) techniques are being considered to quantify aspects of composite deformation, with the benefit of in-situ measurement. Ultrasound C-scan imaging has been demonstrated to possess the requisite resolution to accurately determine fiber fractures [47,49,50], and sequential imaging of strained composite samples allow comparison of the strain experienced by the fiber with the strain applied to the composite (Figure 6, [47,49,50]). Comparisons of broken fiber lengths with theoretical predictions provide a means of assessing whether current modeling techniques are sufficient to account for plasticity and damage in highly deformed regions in single fiber composites. Residual stress measurements can be used as a probe to assess plastic deformation behavior of the matrix. Plastic deformation or damage of the matrix may allow residual stresses in a composite to be relaxed (shakedown), and the measurement of residual fiber stress after various thermal and mechanical treatments (including thermal cycling, tensile testing, fatigue loading, and creep deformation,) can provide insight into the role of plasticity/creep and damage on load relaxation in MMC's. In fact, the residual axial fiber stresses present in an MMC after consolidation have been measured to be significantly reduced after straining the composite to failure [22].

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, the effects of matrix deformation characteristics on the tensile behavior of MMC's has been discussed, with particular attention to the roles of yield strain and work-hardening rate on the global stress-strain response and the evolution of local matrix plasticity in 0° MMC's. Since the global response of the MMC is dominated by the modulus and failure strain of elastic fibers, it is not possible to assess whether analytical/computational models are able to accurately predict local stresses and strains, which in turn control damage evolution and failure mechanisms. The problem is compounded by the fact that local chemistry and microstructural variations give rise to in-situ matrix properties which may be quite different from those of the base matrix properties, and which may vary with distance from the fiber. Cases in point include beta-depleted zones in alpha-2-based MMCs, and carbon-rich areas in most Ti-based MMCs reinforced with SiC fibers. Additionally, inhomogeneous deformation and damage accumulation in the matrix give rise to local strain/stress concentrations, which are not accounted for in most current models. In the case of off-axis systems (such as the 90° MMC), the role of matrix deformation on MMC behavior is even more important.

The amount of increased accuracy and confidence in the ability to model and predict both global and local composite response that is possible via modeling activities is not yet clear. Further, the extent of the material data base required to support this modeling activity is not known. However, the type and amount of data required (including monotonic and time-dependent

properties, temperature and rate effects, interface bond strength measurements, under both simple and complex thermo-mechanical loading conditions) is likely to be a barrier to the use of modeling as a specific guide in composite development activities where the matrix composition and microstructure change frequently. It does seem clear that a strong experimental activity, coupled with close collaboration with the modeling community, is an important approach to improving the understanding of the influence of matrix deformation on MMC properties. Various direct and indirect techniques to assess local matrix deformation are discussed in this paper, and examples are provided from work in progress. These include the use of reference grids to measure local strains, the use of C-scans and ultrasonic imaging to determine damage, and measuring residual strains in the fibers of MMCs subjected to different thermo-mechanical loading histories. Such measurements allow assessment of the roles of matrix plasticity, chemical heterogeneities, microstructural variations, and damage evolution on MMC behavior, and may allow preliminary estimation (in conjunction with iterative modeling schemes) of at least a few constitutive properties at the microscopic level. A basic understanding of the role of matrix variables on MMC properties would also be a very important tool in the development of optimum MMC microstructures for specific structural applications.

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Figure 1. (a) Tensile stress-strain behavior of a 90° SCS-6/Ti-15V-3Cr-3Sn-3Al MMC and comparisons with AGLPLY and unit-cell models. The experimental data and the prediction of the unit cell model include an unloading/reloading cycle. (b) The instantaneous Poisson's ratios compared with the model predictions [19].

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Micrographs of (a) a Ti-6Al-4V (wt%)/SCS-6 MMC, showing a higher volume fraction of the (white) alpha-Ti phase near the fibers, and (b) a Ti-24Al-11Nb/SCS-6 MMC, showing a region depleted in the (white) beta-Ti phase, extending about 10 μm from the fiber. Note that cracks are observed in this beta-depleted zone. An enhancement in the C concentration has been observed up to 50 μm from the fiber in each of these composites [22].

Figure 3. Calculated effects of (a) yield strength (or equivalently, yield strain) of the matrix on the global stress-strain behavior of the MMC, and on the local effective plastic strain in the matrix surrounding the fiber; and (b) work-hardening rate of the matrix and volume fraction of fibers on the global and local response in the MMC. The strain along the y-axis is the local matrix plastic strain at the fiber/matrix interface, and is calculated relative to a strain-free condition at the processing temperature of 815 C. The closed symbols represent composite stress values, and the open symbols indicate the local matrix plastic strain.

Figure 4. (a) Micrograph showing slip bands (sb) in a 0° MMC tensile tested to approximately 1% strain. The micrograph also shows reaction-zone cracks (A), localized excess plasticity around those cracks (B), and debonds (C). (b) Micrograph showing slip bands and debonds in a 90° SCS6/Ti-15-3 MMC pulled to failure at room temperature. Note the intense slip band activity between some of the adjacent fibers.

Figure 5. Optical micrograph of a fiducial reference grid deposited on a Ti-24Al-11Nb/SiC composite. The composite was loaded in the direction indicated. Features illustrated include matrix/fiber debonding, reaction zone cracking, and intense localized plasticity at the equatorial positions of the fiber. The grid pattern was produced using standard photolithographic techniques, and was plasma-etched into the surface to a depth of about 50 nm. Differential interference contrast was used to produce the image. The grid pitch (repeat distance) is 10 μm .

Figure 6. Ultrasound C-scan images of a single fiber composite strained sequentially in tension, illustrating progressive fragmentation of the fiber [50]. The top image was taken after acoustic emission indicated the first fiber fracture, and subsequent images were taken after increasing increments of imposed strain. The sample was not unloaded during imaging.